

Methodology of improving students' speech through the use of dictionaries

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Аннотация: В данной статье рассказывается об использовании уроков родного языка для учащихся начальных классов, важности учебников и методах использования словарей на уроках.

Ключевые слова: Правила развития речи, лексикология, правила этики, лексикология, методика, неактивная лексика.

Abstract: This article talks about the use of native language lessons for primary school students, the importance of textbooks, and methods of using dictionaries in lessons.

Key words: Rules of speech development, lexicology, rules of ethics, Lexicology, methodology, inactive vocabulary.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilariga ona tili darslaridan foydalanish, darslikning ahamiyati, dars mashg'ulotlarida lug'atlardan foydalanish metodikalari haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Nutq o'stirish qoidalari, lug'atshunoslik, axloq qoidalari, Leksikologiya, metodika, nafaol lug'at.

What is speech development? If the student and his/her language activities are taken into account, speech development means active and practical learning of the language in all aspects (pronunciation, vocabulary, syntactic structure, connected speech). If the teacher is concerned, the development of speech is understood as the use of methods and types of work that help students acquire the pronunciation, vocabulary, syntactic construction and connected speech as an important asset. For speech activities, also, in order to develop students' speech, it is necessary to observe several conditions:

There must be a requirement for human speech to emerge. The methodological requirement of developing student speech is to create a situation in which the student expresses his opinion, the desire and need to express something verbally or in writing.

Any speech should have content and material. The more complete, rich, and valuable this material is, the more meaningful its description will be. An idea is understandable only if it is expressed using a word, a phrase, a sentence, and a speech phrase that the listener understands. Therefore, the third condition for successful development of speech is arming speech with language tools.

There are several aspects of speech acquisition. These are: Learning the norms of the literary language. Mastering the essential speaking skills that every member of our society needs, namely reading and writing skills. Improving students' speech culture. In the development of speech, three directions are clearly distinguished:

-word work;

- work on phraseology and sentences;
- work on connected speech.

Lexicology (together with phraseology and stylistics), morphology, syntax serves as the linguistic base for working on words, phrases and sentences; and connected speech is based on logic, literary studies and linguistics of complex syntactic integrity. Consistency in the development of speech is ensured by increasing the ability to subjugate four conditions, that is, consistency, perspective, diversity, different types to a common goal. Types of speech. People use language as a tool for expressing ideas. They think about their thoughts before they voice them. This is internal speech. Inner speech is unheard and unwritten, "thought" (thought) speech. External speech is speech addressed to others, whether it is voiced using sounds or written with graphic symbols. Internal speech helps to understand and remember the material. According to the method of expression, speech is oral and written. Oral speech is often in the form of a dialogue, and written speech is in the form of a monologue. Requirements for students' speech:

- Students' speech should be meaningful.
- Let there be logic in the speech.
- Let the speech be clear.
- Let the speech be rich in language tools.
- Let the speech be clear.
- Let the speech be expressive.
- Let the speech be correct.

- Let the speech be civilized.

Speech is an important tool in developing students' thinking. Speech is not only a means of expression of thought, but also a tool of its formation. Thought serves as the psychological basis of speech, and the condition for its growth is the enrichment of thought. It is possible to successfully develop speech only on the basis of mastering the system of mental activity. That's why great importance is attached to the preparation, improvement of the material, selection of the topic, placement, and logical operations for the development of students' speech. Thought grows successfully only if it is verbally formed and expressed using language material. Concept is expressed by words or phrases, so concept becomes an important communication material in word, which is a language tool. Only if a person knows the word (combination of words) that expresses a concept, based on this concept, he has the opportunity to think in external speech. "Speech is closely connected with thinking. If there is no speech, there is no thinking, and if there is no material of language, it is impossible to express the thought." Verbal formation of thought ensures that it is clear, understandable, pure, consistent, logical. Acquiring a language prepares the conditions for learning the phonetics, vocabulary, and grammatical structure of this language, for improving thought, and for developing thinking.

Knowledge, facts, all kinds of information are the material of thought and speech. Speech serves as an important means of learning the thought process. Speech is used as one of the main measures of the student's intellectual

development. When thinking about the student's mastery of material from all subjects and general mental development, it is focused on how the child can express this or that topic in his speech (written essay, information, retelling, answer to questions). Thus, speech cannot be separated from thinking, speech develops on the basis of thinking; the thought matures and emerges with the help of speech. On the second hand, the growth of speech helps to form and improve thought. On the third hand, the growth of speech helps to form thought and improves it. The connection of students' speech development with other types of training. The development of students' speech is organically connected with activities conducted in other educational subjects. In the mother tongue classes, students learn about nature and people's lives with the help of language; they learn to observe, to think, and to make accurate statements based on what they see, hear, and read. Native language classes effectively help to enrich the child's vocabulary, teach speech structure. The study lesson and the excursion conducted in connection with it provide students with knowledge about natural phenomena, people's life and work, moral rules, norms of dealing with other people; in this lesson, there is a wide opportunity for the student's speech, its formation and growth. With special language learning in grammar and spelling lessons, children learn to hear and say individual sounds, syllables, words and sentences.

They include many words denoting object, action, sign, as well as sound, letter, syllable, stem, word, word-former, form-former, suffix, word group, noun, adjective, number, verb, pronoun, conjunction, sentence, part of sentence, primary

clause, secondary clause, demonstrative sentence, interrogative sentence, exclamatory sentence; they will learn many new terms such as type, conjugation.

As a result, students have the following:

- Understanding, managing and creating effective oral, written and multimedia communication of various forms and content;
- Ability to analyze, evaluate, and manage information in various forms and tools; consider different perspectives;
- Ability to work in a team and demonstrate leadership skills;
- able to accept different roles and responsibilities;
- able to work effectively with others;
- be kind to others;
- the formation of life skills, such as paying attention to different perspectives, is guaranteed.

In conclusion, any speech is grammatically interconnected, with a certain consistency of words and phrases suitable for the content is made from placement. The more rich and developed a person's vocabulary is, the richer his speech will be; ample opportunity is created for him to express his opinion clearly and expressively. Therefore, the richness, variety, mobility of the vocabulary is an important condition for the successful development of speech in the methodology. The modern Uzbek literary language has a huge vocabulary. More than 80,000 words and phrases are given in the five-volume "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language", which are commonly used. If we add to this the words given in

various terminological dictionaries published in Uzbek language, synonyms, antonyms, phraseological dictionaries and various explanatory dictionaries, the wealth of the vocabulary will increase by thousands. In addition, many words mean many things. For example, in this explanatory dictionary, the use of the word head in more than 40 basic and phraseology-related meanings is given. One of the important tasks of speech development at school is to improve the work on the dictionary, to organize it, to define its main directions. Distinguishing and justifying is the management of the process of enriching students' vocabulary.

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